

ISic2943

I.Sicily inscription 2943

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

SG 91, SAS 3

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG2228

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332186

1. [— —] QNOΣ [— —]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644852

PHI 332186

Bibliography

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